

Non-Orthogonality and Misalignment Corrections for 3-Axis Magnetometers

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Abstract

It is difficult to accurately determine and place the individual magnetic axes of a 3-axis flux-gate magnetometer orthogonal to one-another and in-line with the orthogonal axes of the case in which these sensors are embedded.

Derivations and procedures to remove these errors of misalignment and non-orthogonality are presented. Computations then provide components of the local geomagnetic field along the orthogonal case-axes of the magnetometer as a function of the measured D.C. voltage outputs from the flux-gate electronic circuitry. The measurements required for corrections are made using rotations of the triad flux-gate package in the horizontal plane on a test stand using only the local geomagnetic field. The local total geomagnetic field intensity and magnetic dip angle are required, and these can be obtained from measurements using a single axis magnetic flux-gate sensor and a single Helmholtz coil that can be oriented in azimuth and in slant angle. For this, a null method is used whereby the Helmholtz coil current and orientation are adjusted so as to produce zero net magnetic field at the location of the sensor.

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1 Non-Orthogonal Magnetic Flux-Gate Arrays

A typical three-axis magnetometer consists of three magnetic flux-gate sensors and appropriate electronic circuitry mounted in a package or case such that the sensitive axes of the sensors are mutually orthogonal. The flux-gates have one or more primary coils for A.C. excitation, one or more secondary coil(s) for second harmonic A.C. output, and probably an additional secondary coil(s), a "null" coil for use in a negative feedback circuit. The electronic circuitry consists of drivers for primary coil excitation and signal conditioning for the outputs of the sensors. The signal conditioner consists

of three synchronous demodulators, filters and amplifiers. These electronic circuits may be installed in the same package or connected to it by short cables.

The package or case in which the sensors are installed have well defined orthogonal case-axes. The flux-gates are installed in this package with the intention of having one sensor-axis directed along each of the case-axes. If the sensor package is in the shape of, for example, a rectangular parallelepiped (a box), most likely the sides of the package will have been chosen as the orthogonal case-axes. If the sensor package is in the shape of a short circular cylinder, lines will have probably been inscribed on the upper surface to indicate coordinates x and y , with z understood to be normal to the upper surface. The case-axes x, y, z are mutually perpendicular and form a right handed coordinate system.

Ideally, the magnetic sensor-axes u, v, w are the same as the case-axes x, y, z . But ideal situations do not always prevail. A small amount of non-orthogonality between the flux-gate sensor-axes and the misalignment with the case axes will occur, because of the difficulty in their placement and difficulty in accurately ascertaining the orientation of the magnetic axes relative to one-another and to the case-axes. There will usually be some alignment error, albeit small. Indeed, that is the only reason for axes labels u, v, w different from x, y, z . If there were no non-orthogonality and misalignment, there would be no purpose in using the symbols u, v, w for the sensor-axes. Equations for computing the sensor alignment errors based upon the azimuth table measurements and a procedure to remove the alignment errors will be presented.

1.1 Method of Conducting Measurements

The azimuth table of the test stand is set up in the horizontal plane on a test stand. This is accomplished with the use of a bull's eye spirit level. Measurements are obtained by rotating the sensor package in the horizontal plane only, which we shall refer to as the azimuth or co-azimuth plane. The azimuth angle indicating direction of the sensor package rotation in the horizontal plane is Z .

Consider the static sensitivities of the associated signal conditioner (synchronous demodulators, filters and amplifiers). $\varphi_u(\alpha)$ is the x-channel DC output voltage, $\varphi_v(\alpha)$ is the y-channel DC output voltage and $\varphi_w(\alpha)$ is the z-channel DC output voltage. The input voltages to the signal conditioner are the second harmonic A.C. outputs of the magnetic flux-gates on the u, v, w sensor axes. The static sensitivities are

$$l_1 = \frac{\varphi_u}{B_u}, \quad l_2 = \frac{\varphi_v}{B_v}, \quad l_3 = \frac{\varphi_w}{B_w} \quad (1)$$

where B_u, B_v, B_w are components of the local geomagnetic field intensity along the sensor axes. Ultimately, from our measurements of D.C. sensor voltages we will

be able to compute the components of the geomagnetic field along the *orthogonal* case-axes B_x, B_y, B_z of the magnetometer.

Before conducting measurements, we independently attempt to adjust signal conditioner static sensitivities l_1, l_2 and l_3 to be equal to one another. These are measured, e.g., in volts/gauss. After measurements are completed, l_1, l_2 and l_3 will then be found to be approximately equal to one another. Their exact values will be computed using data from measurements on the test stand by equations derived in this paper.

Note: The w -axis sensor (associated with the vertical z -axis) experiences much smaller excursions of the magnetic field along its axis than the u -axis and v -axis sensors when the sensor triad is rotated in the horizontal plane, and indeed does not experience a change in direction of the magnetic field along that axis. For computing the magnetic static sensitivity along the w -axis sensor and the directional cosines for that sensor-axis, it is perhaps advisable to conduct a second round of rotations with that w sensor-axis lying in the horizontal plane.

Angle Formats Since our azimuth table most likely has an azimuth circle rather than one scaled for co-azimuth, we make measurements at equal increments of azimuth and then replace azimuth angle Z with the equivalent co-azimuth angle α in our equations. After most computations are completed, we can replace co-azimuth α with the equivalent azimuth Z .

In standard mathematical angle format, co-azimuth α is a positive angle measured CCW from the N (magnetic North) axis looking downward onto the horizontal plane. In navigational angle format, azimuth Z is a positive angle measured CW from the N axis looking downward onto the horizontal plane¹.

¹CW = clockwise, CCW = counter-clockwise.

Figure 1: A Sample Rotation in the Test Fixture.

$Z = 360^\circ - \alpha = -\alpha$ and $\cos Z = \cos \alpha$, $\sin Z = -\sin \alpha$.

When $Z = 0$, the x body-axis is pointed in the direction of magnetic north.

As we shall demonstrate in this paper, due to misalignment of sensor axes in the sensor package, the output voltages from the x -axis sensor, the y -axis sensor and the z -axis sensor for rotations in the horizontal plane will be of the forms

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varphi_u(\alpha) &= a_{01} + A_1 \cos \alpha + B_1 \sin \alpha &\Rightarrow &\varphi_u(Z) = a_{01} + A_1 \cos Z - B_1 \sin Z \\
 \varphi_v(\alpha) &= a_{02} + A_2 \cos \alpha + B_2 \sin \alpha &\Rightarrow &\varphi_v(Z) = a_{02} + A_2 \cos Z - B_2 \sin Z \\
 \varphi_w(\alpha) &= a_{03} + A_3 \cos \alpha + B_3 \sin \alpha &\Rightarrow &\varphi_w(Z) = a_{03} + A_3 \cos Z - B_3 \sin Z
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2}$$

As Z is increased from 0 to 360° in equal increments by rotating the sensor package, φ_u should vary as $\cos Z$ if there are no alignment errors and φ_v should vary as $-\sin Z$ if there are no alignment errors.

We use plus signs instead of minus signs in front of B_1 , B_2 and B_3 in the three equations above using α , because subsequent evaluation of these coefficients in each equation involves a numerical integration which most directly proceeds with this format. (The symbols B_1 , B_2 and B_3 herein do not represent magnetic field intensities; they are simply constants).

From these equations we can infer that

$$\cos \alpha = \cos Z = \frac{(B_2 \varphi_u - B_1 \varphi_v) - (a_{01} B_2 - a_{02} B_1)}{A_1 B_2 - A_2 B_1}$$

Similarly,

$$\sin \alpha = -\sin Z = -\frac{(A_2 \varphi_u - A_1 \varphi_v) - (a_1 A_{02} - a_2 A_{01})}{A_1 B_2 - B_1 A_2}$$

If we measure the voltages φ_u and φ_v , we then determine the (quadrant justified) uncorrected co-azimuth α using

$$\alpha = \text{atn2}(\cos \alpha, \sin \alpha)$$

Computing the Best Fit Equations for φ_u , φ_v and φ_w

Consider a function $y(\theta)$ expanded into a Fourier series:

$$y(\theta) = a_0 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (A_k \cos k \theta + B_k \sin k \theta) \quad (3)$$

where k is the harmonic number. In this paper, we express angles in degrees rather than in radians, so

$$\frac{\theta}{2\pi} = \frac{\theta_{\text{deg}}}{360} \Rightarrow d\theta = \frac{2\pi}{360} d\theta_{\text{deg}}.$$

After making the radian to degree conversions, and dropping the "deg." subscript from θ .

$$a_0 \leftarrow a_k = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} y(\theta) d\theta = \frac{1}{360} \int_0^{360} y(\theta) d\theta \quad (4)$$

$$A_k = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} y(\theta) \cos k\theta d\theta = \frac{2}{360} \int_0^{360} y(\theta) \cos k\theta d\theta \quad (5)$$

$$B_k = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} y(\theta) \sin k\theta d\theta = \frac{2}{360} \int_0^{360} y(\theta) \sin k\theta d\theta \quad (6)$$

Keep in mind that the integral for a_0 has a $\frac{1}{2\pi}$ factor, whereas the integrals for A_k and B_k have a $\frac{1}{\pi}$ factor.

Recall that the average value of a function $y(\theta)$ over the interval $[a, b]$ is

$$\bar{y}(\theta) = \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b y(\theta) d\theta$$

Thus, the equations for a_k , A_k and B_k above express averages.

Successively make the following symbol replacements:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta &\leftarrow \alpha, & y(\theta) &\leftarrow \varphi_u(\alpha), & A_k &\leftarrow A_1(k), & B_k &\leftarrow B_1(k), & a_k &\leftarrow a_{01} \\ & & y(\theta) &\leftarrow \varphi_v(\alpha), & A_k &\leftarrow A_2(k), & B_k &\leftarrow B_2(k), & a_k &\leftarrow a_{02} \\ & & y(\theta) &\leftarrow \varphi_w(\alpha), & A_k &\leftarrow A_3(k), & B_k &\leftarrow B_3(k), & a_k &\leftarrow a_{03} \end{aligned}$$

We can then write (for finite N)

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_u(\alpha) &\approx a_{01} + \sum_{k=1}^N [A_1(k) \cos k \alpha + B_1(k) \sin k \alpha] \\ \varphi_v(\alpha) &\approx a_{02} + \sum_{k=1}^N [A_2(k) \cos k \alpha + B_2(k) \sin k \alpha] \\ \varphi_w(\alpha) &\approx a_{03} + \sum_{k=1}^N [A_3(k) \cos k \alpha + B_3(k) \sin k \alpha]\end{aligned}$$

We can also write the summations as

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_u(\alpha) &\approx \sum_{k=0}^N [A_1(k) \cos k \alpha + B_1(k) \sin k \alpha] \\ \varphi_v(\alpha) &\approx \sum_{k=0}^N [A_2(k) \cos k \alpha + B_2(k) \sin k \alpha] \\ \varphi_w(\alpha) &\approx \sum_{k=0}^N [A_3(k) \cos k \alpha + B_3(k) \sin k \alpha] \\ &\text{with } A_1(0) = a_{01}, \quad A_2(0) = a_{02} \quad \text{and} \quad A_3(0) = a_{03}\end{aligned}$$

In a computer program, we might ignore all harmonics except the first ($k = 1$) and write $A_1(1) = A_1$, $B_1(1) = B_1$, $A_2(1) = A_2$, $B_2(1) = B_2$, $A_3(1) = A_3$, $B_3(1) = B_3$. We can determine these coefficients using numerical integrations, either rectangular, trapezoidal or parabolic (Simpson's Rule). The ignored higher harmonics might be regarded as truncation and round-off errors.

$$\theta \leftarrow \theta_k, \quad d\theta \leftarrow \Delta\theta = \frac{b-a}{N} = \frac{360-0}{N} = \frac{360}{N},$$

where N is the number of parts into which the azimuth circle is divided.

The simplest of these is rectangular integration. However, trapezoidal and parabolic numerical integration are more accurate. We will employ Simpsons rule (parabolic integration).

$$\text{Rectangular, } \int_a^b y(\theta) d\theta \approx \Delta\theta \sum_{k=0}^N y_k, \text{ e.g., } \Delta\theta (y_0 + y_1 + y_2 + y_3).$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Trapezoidal, } \int_a^b y(\theta) d\theta &\approx \Delta\theta \sum_{k=0}^N p_k y_k, \text{ e.g., } \Delta\theta \left(\frac{1}{2}y_0 + y_1 + y_2 + \frac{1}{2}y_3\right) \\ &\text{where } p_k = \frac{1}{2} \text{ if } k = 0 \text{ or } N, \text{ else } p_k = 1.\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Parabolic, } \int_a^b y(\theta) d\theta \approx \frac{\Delta\theta}{3} \sum_{k=0}^N p_k y_k, \text{ i.e.,}$$

$$\int_a^b y(\theta) d\theta \approx \frac{\Delta\theta}{3} (y_0 + 4y_1 + 2y_2 + 4y_3 + \dots + 4y_{N-2} + 2y_{N-1} + y_N),$$

$$\text{where } p_k = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } k = 0 \text{ or } N \\ 2 & \text{if } k = 2, 4, 6, 8, \dots, \text{etc. (even numbered } k) \\ 4 & \text{if } k = 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, \dots, \text{etc. (odd numbered } k) \end{cases}$$

$$a_k = \frac{1}{360} \int_0^{360} y(\theta) d\theta \leftarrow \frac{1}{360} \frac{360}{N} \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=0}^N p_k y(\theta_k) = \frac{1}{3N} \sum_{k=0}^N p_k y(\theta_k) \quad (7)$$

$$A_k = 2 \frac{1}{360} \int_0^{360} y(\theta) \cos k\theta d\theta \leftarrow \frac{2}{360} \frac{360}{N} \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=0}^N p_k y(\theta_k) \cos k(\Delta\theta) = \frac{2}{3N} \sum_{k=0}^N p_k y(\theta_k) \cos k \left(\frac{360}{N} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$B_k = 2 \frac{1}{360} \int_0^{360} y(\theta) \sin k\theta d\theta \leftarrow \frac{2}{360} \frac{360}{N} \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=0}^N p_k y(\theta_k) \sin k(\Delta\theta) = \frac{2}{3N} \sum_{k=0}^N p_k y(\theta_k) \sin k \left(\frac{360}{N} \right) \quad (9)$$

1.1.1 Sensor, Case & Laboratory Axes

What we call the earth's "north magnetic pole" is really a south magnetic pole in terms of physics. Physicists regard the northward magnetic flux density as negative; however, by convention we disregard this as irrelevant in these derivations and measurements and regard the northward geomagnetic flux density as positive. We use the terms "azimuth table", "plane table", "test fixture" and "test stand" interchangeably.

Magnetic Dip Angle The component array

$$B_{lab} = \begin{pmatrix} B_{North} \\ B_{West} \\ B_{Zenith} \end{pmatrix} = B \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta \\ 0 \\ \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix} = B \begin{pmatrix} \cos D \\ 0 \\ -\sin D \end{pmatrix} \quad (10)$$

consists of the orthogonal laboratory-axes components of the local geomagnetic field intensity \mathbf{B} .

D is the magnetic dip angle and Δ is the magnetic co-dip angle.

Magnetic dip angle is the angle at which the local geomagnetic flux-density vector \mathbf{B} points below the local horizontal plane and is measured positively downward below the horizontal plane and negatively above the horizontal plane. $D \in [-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$.

Δ = Magnetic co-dip angle; $\Delta \in [0, 180^\circ]$. The co-dip angle Δ is the spherical coordinate slant angle of the local geomagnetic flux-density vector \mathbf{B} measured from the zenith. Magnetic co-dip angle $\Delta = D + 90^\circ$.

$\sin \Delta = \cos D$, $\cos \Delta = -\sin D$, $\tan \Delta = -\cot D$ and $\cot \Delta = -\tan D$.

In derivations we may, if we so choose, replace terms involving Δ by their equivalents using D .

$$B_{case} = Z(\alpha) B_{lab}, \text{ i.e., } \begin{matrix} \text{Case-Axes} \\ \text{Components} \end{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} B_x \\ B_y \\ B_z \end{pmatrix} = Z(\alpha) \begin{matrix} \text{Lab-Axes} \\ \text{Components} \end{matrix} \begin{pmatrix} B_{North} \\ B_{West} \\ B_{Zenith} \end{pmatrix} \quad (11)$$

are the case-axes components of the local geomagnetic field intensity *for the sensor case installed on the azimuth table* (which table lies in the horizontal plane). $Z(\alpha)$ is the plane table rotation matrix.

B_x, B_y, B_z are the components of the geomagnetic field along the mutually perpendicular case-axes of the sensor frame or case. These case-axes are rotated on the test fixture by angle $Z = 360^\circ - \alpha$ relative to the the laboratory-axes fixed in the earth.

In engineering parlance, we might regard the geomagnetic field along the case-axes, which field is known on the test stand, as an input signal (the source), the magnetic sensor array (the sink), and sensor output voltages as output signals, which are also known from our measurements. These two signals, the input and output signals, are related to one another by the direction cosine matrix, which we may regard as the transfer function of this part of the system and which can be determined from these inputs and outputs.

$$B_{case} = \begin{pmatrix} B_x \\ B_y \\ B_z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha & \sin \alpha & 0 \\ -\sin \alpha & \cos \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} B \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta \\ 0 \\ \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix}, \text{ i.e.,} \quad (12)$$

$$B_{case} = B \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta \cos \alpha \\ -\sin \Delta \sin \alpha \\ \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix} = B \begin{pmatrix} \cos D \cos \alpha \\ -\cos D \sin \alpha \\ -\sin D \end{pmatrix} \quad (13)$$

or

$$B_{case} = B \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\sin \Delta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha \\ \sin \alpha \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (14)$$

1.1.2 Non-Orthogonal Sensor Coordinates

Let $\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}$ be the orthogonal unit vectors along the case-axes (x, y, z) , with \mathbf{i} and \mathbf{j} lying in the horizontal plane when the sensor case is situated on the plane table of the test fixture.

(u, v, w) is a set of non-orthogonal sensor-axes with unit vectors $(\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3)$. See Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Direction cosines, Case-axes and Sensor-axes.

In Figure 2 (a), α, β and γ represent the orientation angles of an arbitrary vector \mathbf{R} in the orthogonal case-axis coordinate system. \mathbf{e}_R is the radial unit vector. The cosines of these angles are the *direction cosines* of that vector. In Figure 2 (b), u, v and w are the non-orthogonal sensor-axes and $\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2$ and \mathbf{e}_3 are their unit vectors.

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{i}x + \mathbf{j}y + \mathbf{k}z = (\mathbf{i}, \mathbf{j}, \mathbf{k}) \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{i} = |\mathbf{R}| |\mathbf{i}| \cos(\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{i}) = R \cos(R, x) = R \cos \alpha \\ y &= \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{j} = |\mathbf{R}| |\mathbf{j}| \cos(\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{j}) = R \cos(R, y) = R \cos \beta \\ z &= \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{k} = |\mathbf{R}| |\mathbf{k}| \cos(\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{k}) = R \cos(R, z) = R \cos \gamma \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{R} = (\mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{i}) \mathbf{i} + (\mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{j}) \mathbf{j} + (\mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{k}) \mathbf{k}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \therefore \mathbf{R} &= \mathbf{e}_R R = \mathbf{i} R \cos \alpha + \mathbf{j} R \cos \beta + \mathbf{k} R \cos \gamma \\ \Rightarrow \mathbf{e}_R &= \mathbf{i} \cos \alpha + \mathbf{j} \cos \beta + \mathbf{k} \cos \gamma \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\frac{x}{R} = \cos \alpha, \quad \frac{y}{R} = \cos \beta, \quad \frac{z}{R} = \cos \gamma$$

where $\cos \alpha, \cos \beta, \cos \gamma$ are the direction cosines of the vector \mathbf{R} , with $R = |\mathbf{R}|$.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{e}_R \cdot \mathbf{R} &= (\mathbf{i} \cos \alpha + \mathbf{j} \cos \beta + \mathbf{k} \cos \gamma) \cdot (\mathbf{i}x + \mathbf{j}y + \mathbf{k}z) \\ \Rightarrow \mathbf{e}_R \cdot \mathbf{R} &= R = x \cos \alpha + y \cos \beta + z \cos \gamma \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
R^2 &= \mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{R} = (R \cos \alpha)^2 + (R \cos \beta)^2 + (R \cos \gamma)^2 \\
&\Rightarrow \cos^2 \alpha + \cos^2 \beta + \cos^2 \gamma = 1
\end{aligned}$$

In the remainder of this paper we will have no further use for the unsubscripted symbols α, β, γ for angle measurements.

Repeating $\mathbf{R} = (\mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{i}) \mathbf{i} + (\mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{j}) \mathbf{j} + (\mathbf{R} \cdot \mathbf{k}) \mathbf{k}$ and successively letting $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w}$ and $\mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2, \mathbf{e}_3$ (the unit vectors along the u, v, w axes), we have...

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{u} &= \mathbf{e}_1 u = \mathbf{i} u \cos(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{i}) + \mathbf{j} u \cos(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{j}) + \mathbf{k} u \cos(\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{k}) \\
&= \mathbf{i} u \cos(u, x) + \mathbf{j} u \cos(u, y) + \mathbf{k} u \cos(u, z) \\
&= \mathbf{i} u \cos \alpha_{11} + \mathbf{j} u \cos \alpha_{12} + \mathbf{k} u \cos \alpha_{13}
\end{aligned}$$

Letting $u_x = u \cos \alpha_{11}$, $u_y = u \cos \alpha_{12}$, $u_z = u \cos \alpha_{13}$, we can write $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{i} u_x + \mathbf{j} u_y + \mathbf{k} u_z$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{v} &= \mathbf{e}_2 v = \mathbf{i} v \cos(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{i}) + \mathbf{j} v \cos(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{j}) + \mathbf{k} v \cos(\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{k}) \\
&= \mathbf{i} v \cos(v, x) + \mathbf{j} v \cos(v, y) + \mathbf{k} v \cos(v, z) \\
&= \mathbf{i} v \cos \alpha_{21} + \mathbf{j} v \cos \alpha_{22} + \mathbf{k} v \cos \alpha_{23}
\end{aligned}$$

Letting $v_x = v \cos \alpha_{21}$, $v_y = v \cos \alpha_{22}$, $v_z = v \cos \alpha_{23}$, we can write $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{i} v_x + \mathbf{j} v_y + \mathbf{k} v_z$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{w} &= \mathbf{e}_3 w = \mathbf{i} w \cos(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{i}) + \mathbf{j} w \cos(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{j}) + \mathbf{k} w \cos(\mathbf{w}, \mathbf{k}) \\
&= \mathbf{i} w \cos(w, x) + \mathbf{j} w \cos(w, y) + \mathbf{k} w \cos(w, z) \\
&= \mathbf{i} w \cos \alpha_{31} + \mathbf{j} w \cos \alpha_{32} + \mathbf{k} w \cos \alpha_{33}
\end{aligned}$$

Letting $w_x = w \cos \alpha_{31}$, $w_y = w \cos \alpha_{32}$, $w_z = w \cos \alpha_{33}$, we can write $\mathbf{w} = \mathbf{i} w_x + \mathbf{j} w_y + \mathbf{k} w_z$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{e}_1 &= (\mathbf{e}_1 \cdot \mathbf{i}) \mathbf{i} + (\mathbf{e}_1 \cdot \mathbf{j}) \mathbf{j} + (\mathbf{e}_1 \cdot \mathbf{k}) \mathbf{k} \\
&= \mathbf{i} \cos \alpha_{11} + \mathbf{j} \cos \alpha_{12} + \mathbf{k} \cos \alpha_{13}
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{e}_2 &= (\mathbf{e}_2 \cdot \mathbf{i}) \mathbf{i} + (\mathbf{e}_2 \cdot \mathbf{j}) \mathbf{j} + (\mathbf{e}_2 \cdot \mathbf{k}) \mathbf{k} \\
&= \mathbf{i} \cos \alpha_{21} + \mathbf{j} \cos \alpha_{22} + \mathbf{k} \cos \alpha_{23}
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{e}_3 &= (\mathbf{e}_3 \cdot \mathbf{i}) \mathbf{i} + (\mathbf{e}_3 \cdot \mathbf{j}) \mathbf{j} + (\mathbf{e}_3 \cdot \mathbf{k}) \mathbf{k} \\
&= \mathbf{i} \cos \alpha_{31} + \mathbf{j} \cos \alpha_{32} + \mathbf{k} \cos \alpha_{33}
\end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{e}_1 \\ \mathbf{e}_2 \\ \mathbf{e}_3 \end{pmatrix} &= C \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{i} \\ \mathbf{j} \\ \mathbf{k} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{i} \\ \mathbf{j} \\ \mathbf{k} \end{pmatrix} = C^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{e}_1 \\ \mathbf{e}_2 \\ \mathbf{e}_3 \end{pmatrix} \\
C &= \begin{pmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & c_{13} \\ c_{21} & c_{22} & c_{23} \\ c_{31} & c_{32} & c_{33} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha_{11} & \cos \alpha_{12} & \cos \alpha_{13} \\ \cos \alpha_{21} & \cos \alpha_{22} & \cos \alpha_{23} \\ \cos \alpha_{31} & \cos \alpha_{32} & \cos \alpha_{33} \end{pmatrix}
\end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

where C is the *direction cosine matrix* and c_{ij} are direction cosines. C transforms the set of the orthogonal case-axes to the non-orthogonal sensor-axes.

The angles α_{ij} are projection angles of the sensor-axes u, v, w onto the case-axes x, y, z .

$$\begin{array}{llll} \alpha_{11} = \angle(u, x) & \alpha_{12} = \angle(u, y) & \alpha_{13} = \angle(u, z) & \text{For the sake of brevity in writing,} \\ \alpha_{21} = \angle(v, x) & \alpha_{22} = \angle(v, y) & \alpha_{23} = \angle(v, z) & \text{we may dispense with the commas} \\ \alpha_{31} = \angle(w, x) & \alpha_{32} = \angle(w, y) & \alpha_{33} = \angle(w, z) & \text{in the parentheses and the } \angle \text{ symbol.} \end{array}$$

We associate the first subscript of α_{ij} with u, v or w and the second subscript of α_{ij} with x, y or z . That is, we associate $i = 1$ with u , $i = 2$ with v , $i = 3$ with w and $j = 1$ with x , $j = 2$ with y , $j = 3$ with z .

The direction cosine angles are always positive, $\alpha_{ij} \geq 0$, and usually very small. In the usual portrayal of angles in figures, a curve with an arrow at the end, e.g. \curvearrowright , is employed in figures. In portraying direction cosine angles, the arrow is usually directed from a coordinate toward the vector being described.

1.1.3 Relating the Direction Cosines to Measurements

Consider the following scalar products:

$$\begin{aligned} B_u &= \mathbf{B}_{case} \cdot \mathbf{e}_1 = (\mathbf{i} B_x + \mathbf{j} B_y + \mathbf{k} B_z) \cdot (\mathbf{i} \cos \alpha_{11} + \mathbf{j} \cos \alpha_{12} + \mathbf{k} \cos \alpha_{13}) \\ &= B_x \cos \alpha_{11} + B_y \cos \alpha_{12} + B_z \cos \alpha_{13} = c_{11} B_x + c_{12} B_y + c_{13} B_z \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} B_v &= \mathbf{B}_{case} \cdot \mathbf{e}_2 = (\mathbf{i} B_x + \mathbf{j} B_y + \mathbf{k} B_z) \cdot (\mathbf{i} \cos \alpha_{21} + \mathbf{j} \cos \alpha_{22} + \mathbf{k} \cos \alpha_{23}) \\ &= B_x \cos \alpha_{21} + B_y \cos \alpha_{22} + B_z \cos \alpha_{23} = c_{21} B_x + c_{22} B_y + c_{23} B_z \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} B_w &= \mathbf{B}_{case} \cdot \mathbf{e}_3 = (\mathbf{i} B_x + \mathbf{j} B_y + \mathbf{k} B_z) \cdot (\mathbf{i} \cos \alpha_{31} + \mathbf{j} \cos \alpha_{32} + \mathbf{k} \cos \alpha_{33}) \\ &= B_x \cos \alpha_{31} + B_y \cos \alpha_{32} + B_z \cos \alpha_{33} = c_{31} B_x + c_{32} B_y + c_{33} B_z \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} B_u \\ B_v \\ B_w \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{B}_{case} \cdot \mathbf{e}_1 \\ \mathbf{B}_{case} \cdot \mathbf{e}_2 \\ \mathbf{B}_{case} \cdot \mathbf{e}_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & c_{13} \\ c_{21} & c_{22} & c_{23} \\ c_{31} & c_{32} & c_{33} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} B_x \\ B_y \\ B_z \end{pmatrix} = C \begin{pmatrix} B_x \\ B_y \\ B_z \end{pmatrix} = C B_{case}$$

$\boxed{B_{sensor} = C B_{case}}$

(19)

$$\therefore \begin{pmatrix} B_x \\ B_y \\ B_z \end{pmatrix} = C^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} B_u \\ B_v \\ B_w \end{pmatrix} = C^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_u/l_1 \\ \varphi_v/l_2 \\ \varphi_w/l_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

1.1.4 Digression. Comments Regarding the Transpose of the Matrix C .

Suppose $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{e}_1 B_u + \mathbf{e}_2 B_v + \mathbf{e}_3 B_w$.

Let B'_x (notice the prime on B_x) be the sum of the projections of B_u, B_v, B_w onto the x -axis. And similarly for B'_y and B'_z . But B_u, B_v, B_w are themselves projections of $\mathbf{B}_{case} = \mathbf{i} B_x + \mathbf{j} B_y + \mathbf{k} B_z$ onto the u, v, w sensor-axes, so B'_x, B'_y, B'_z are projections of projections.

$$\begin{aligned} B'_x &= (\mathbf{e}_1 B_u + \mathbf{e}_2 B_v + \mathbf{e}_3 B_w) \cdot \mathbf{i} = (\mathbf{e}_1 B_u \cdot \mathbf{i}) + (\mathbf{e}_2 B_v \cdot \mathbf{i}) + (\mathbf{e}_3 B_w \cdot \mathbf{i}) \\ &= B_u \cos \alpha_{11} + B_v \cos \alpha_{21} + B_w \cos \alpha_{31} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} B'_y &= (\mathbf{e}_1 B_u + \mathbf{e}_2 B_v + \mathbf{e}_3 B_w) \cdot \mathbf{j} = (\mathbf{e}_1 B_u \cdot \mathbf{j}) + (\mathbf{e}_2 B_v \cdot \mathbf{j}) + (\mathbf{e}_3 B_w \cdot \mathbf{j}) \\ &= B_u \cos \alpha_{12} + B_v \cos \alpha_{22} + B_w \cos \alpha_{32} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} B'_z &= (\mathbf{e}_1 B_u + \mathbf{e}_2 B_v + \mathbf{e}_3 B_w) \cdot \mathbf{k} = (\mathbf{e}_1 B_u \cdot \mathbf{k}) + (\mathbf{e}_2 B_v \cdot \mathbf{k}) + (\mathbf{e}_3 B_w \cdot \mathbf{k}) \\ &= B_u \cos \alpha_{13} + B_v \cos \alpha_{23} + B_w \cos \alpha_{33} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} B'_x &= B_u \cos \alpha_{11} + B_v \cos \alpha_{21} + B_w \cos \alpha_{31} \\ B'_y &= B_u \cos \alpha_{12} + B_v \cos \alpha_{22} + B_w \cos \alpha_{32} \\ B'_z &= B_u \cos \alpha_{13} + B_v \cos \alpha_{23} + B_w \cos \alpha_{33} \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore B'_{case} = \tilde{C} B_{sensor}$$

\tilde{C} or C^T indicates the transpose of the matrix C .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{But } B_{case} &= C^{-1} B_{sensor} \text{ and } B'_{case} \neq B_{case}, \\ \text{so } B_{case} &\neq \tilde{C} B_{sensor}, \text{ and so, } \boxed{C^{-1} \neq \tilde{C}} \end{aligned}$$

End of digression.

Continuing with our previous line of thought,

$$B_{sensor} = C B_{case} = C Z(\alpha) B_{lab} \quad (20)$$

where the array B_{sensor} consists of the non-orthogonal sensor-axes components of the local geomagnetic field intensity \mathbf{B} , and the array B_{case} consists of the orthogonal case-axes components of \mathbf{B} .

$$\Phi = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_u \\ \varphi_v \\ \varphi_w \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} l_1 B_u \\ l_2 B_v \\ l_3 B_w \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} l_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & l_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & l_3 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} B_u \\ B_v \\ B_w \end{pmatrix} \quad (21)$$

$$\text{or } \Phi = l B_{sensor}, \text{ where } l = \begin{pmatrix} l_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & l_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & l_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (22)$$

$$B_{sensor} = C B_{case} \Rightarrow \Phi(\alpha) = l B_{sensor} = l (C B_{case}) = (lC) B_{case}$$

where

$$B_{case} = \begin{pmatrix} B_x \\ B_y \\ B_z \end{pmatrix} = B \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\sin \Delta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha \\ \sin \alpha \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

From the Simpson's rule numerical integrations,

$$\Phi(\alpha) = \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_u(\alpha) \\ \varphi_v(\alpha) \\ \varphi_w(\alpha) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{01} + A_1 \cos \alpha + B_1 \sin \alpha \\ a_{02} + A_2 \cos \alpha + B_2 \sin \alpha \\ a_{03} + A_3 \cos \alpha + B_3 \sin \alpha \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A_1 & B_1 & a_{01} \\ A_2 & B_2 & a_{02} \\ A_3 & B_3 & a_{03} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha \\ \sin \alpha \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (23)$$

$$\text{Let } J = \begin{pmatrix} A_1 & B_1 & a_{01} \\ A_2 & B_2 & a_{02} \\ A_3 & B_3 & a_{03} \end{pmatrix}, \text{ so } \Phi(\alpha) = J \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha \\ \sin \alpha \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Subtracting one version of $\Phi(\alpha)$ from the other,

$$\left[B \begin{pmatrix} l_1 c_{11} & l_1 c_{12} & l_1 c_{13} \\ l_2 c_{21} & l_2 c_{22} & l_2 c_{23} \\ l_3 c_{31} & l_3 c_{32} & l_3 c_{33} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\sin \Delta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} A_1 & B_1 & a_{01} \\ A_2 & B_2 & a_{02} \\ A_3 & B_3 & a_{03} \end{pmatrix} \right] \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha \\ \sin \alpha \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = 0 \quad (24)$$

and noting that

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\sin \Delta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sin \Delta} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{\sin \Delta} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\cos \Delta} \end{pmatrix}$$

we may write

$$lC = \begin{pmatrix} l_1 c_{11} & l_1 c_{12} & l_1 c_{13} \\ l_2 c_{21} & l_2 c_{22} & l_2 c_{23} \\ l_3 c_{31} & l_3 c_{32} & l_3 c_{33} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{B} \begin{pmatrix} A_1 & B_1 & a_{01} \\ A_2 & B_2 & a_{02} \\ A_3 & B_3 & a_{03} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sin \Delta} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -\frac{1}{\sin \Delta} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\cos \Delta} \end{pmatrix} \quad (25)$$

That is,

$$({}^l C) = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{A_1}{B \sin \Delta} & -\frac{B_1}{B \sin \Delta} & \frac{a_{01}}{B \cos \Delta} \\ \frac{A_2}{B \sin \Delta} & -\frac{B_2}{B \sin \Delta} & \frac{a_{02}}{B \cos \Delta} \\ \frac{A_3}{B \sin \Delta} & -\frac{B_3}{B \sin \Delta} & \frac{a_{03}}{B \cos \Delta} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{B \sin \Delta} \begin{pmatrix} A_1 & -B_1 & a_{01} \tan \Delta \\ A_2 & -B_2 & a_{02} \tan \Delta \\ A_3 & -B_3 & a_{03} \tan \Delta \end{pmatrix} \quad (26)$$

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & c_{13} \\ c_{21} & c_{22} & c_{23} \\ c_{31} & c_{32} & c_{33} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{A_1}{l_1 B \sin \Delta} & -\frac{B_1}{l_1 B \sin \Delta} & \frac{a_{01}}{l_1 B \cos \Delta} \\ \frac{A_2}{l_2 B \sin \Delta} & -\frac{B_2}{l_2 B \sin \Delta} & \frac{a_{02}}{l_2 B \cos \Delta} \\ \frac{A_3}{l_3 B \sin \Delta} & -\frac{B_3}{l_3 B \sin \Delta} & \frac{a_{03}}{l_3 B \cos \Delta} \end{pmatrix} \quad (27)$$

$$\text{or } C = \frac{1}{B \sin \Delta} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{A_1}{l_1} & -\frac{B_1}{l_1} & \frac{a_{01}}{l_1} \tan \Delta \\ \frac{A_2}{l_2} & -\frac{B_2}{l_2} & \frac{a_{02}}{l_2} \tan \Delta \\ \frac{A_3}{l_3} & -\frac{B_3}{l_3} & \frac{a_{03}}{l_3} \tan \Delta \end{pmatrix}$$

$C_{11} = \frac{A_1}{l_1 B \sin \Delta}$	$C_{12} = -\frac{B_1}{l_1 B \sin \Delta}$	$C_{13} = \frac{a_{01}}{l_1 B \cos \Delta}$	(28)
$C_{21} = \frac{A_2}{l_2 B \sin \Delta}$	$C_{22} = -\frac{B_2}{l_2 B \sin \Delta}$	$C_{23} = \frac{a_{02}}{l_2 B \cos \Delta}$	
$C_{31} = \frac{A_3}{l_3 B \sin \Delta}$	$C_{32} = -\frac{B_3}{l_3 B \sin \Delta}$	$C_{33} = \frac{a_{03}}{l_3 B \cos \Delta}$	

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Recalling } \Phi &= {}^l B_{\text{sensor}} = {}^l (C B_{\text{case}}) = ({}^l C) B_{\text{case}}, \\ \text{let } \gamma &= ({}^l C)^{-1} \quad B_{\text{case}} = ({}^l C)^{-1} \Phi = \gamma \Phi \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

$$\gamma = (l C)^{-1} = B \sin \Delta \begin{pmatrix} A_1 & -B_1 & a_{01} \tan \Delta \\ A_2 & -B_2 & a_{02} \tan \Delta \\ A_3 & -B_3 & a_{03} \tan \Delta \end{pmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{A_1}{B \sin \Delta} & -\frac{B_1}{B \sin \Delta} & \frac{a_{01}}{B \cos \Delta} \\ \frac{A_2}{B \sin \Delta} & -\frac{B_2}{B \sin \Delta} & \frac{a_{02}}{B \cos \Delta} \\ \frac{A_3}{B \sin \Delta} & -\frac{B_3}{B \sin \Delta} & \frac{a_{03}}{B \cos \Delta} \end{pmatrix}^{-1} \quad (30)$$

The matrix C^{-1} must be evaluated. For any 3×3 matrix with non-zero determinant the following is true:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b & c \\ d & e & f \\ g & h & i \end{pmatrix}^{-1} = \frac{1}{\det C} \begin{pmatrix} ei - fh & ch - bi & bf - ce \\ fg - di & ai - cg & cd - af \\ dh - eg & bg - ah & ae - bd \end{pmatrix} \quad (31)$$

where

$$\det C = a(ei - fh) + b(fg - di) + c(dh - eg) \quad (32)$$

is the determinant of the original matrix.

Then

$$C^{-1} = \frac{1}{\det C} \begin{pmatrix} c_{22}c_{33} - c_{23}c_{32} & c_{13}c_{32} - c_{12}c_{33} & c_{12}c_{23} - c_{13}c_{22} \\ c_{23}c_{31} - c_{21}c_{33} & c_{11}c_{33} - c_{13}c_{31} & c_{13}c_{21} - c_{11}c_{23} \\ c_{21}c_{32} - c_{22}c_{31} & c_{12}c_{31} - c_{11}c_{32} & c_{11}c_{22} - c_{12}c_{21} \end{pmatrix} \quad (33)$$

where

$$\det C = c_{11}(c_{22}c_{33} - c_{23}c_{32}) + c_{12}(c_{23}c_{31} - c_{21}c_{33}) + c_{13}(c_{21}c_{32} - c_{22}c_{31}) \quad (34)$$

$$\det C = -\frac{[a_{01}(A_2B_3 - A_3B_2) + a_{02}(A_3B_1 - A_1B_3) + a_{03}(A_1B_2 - A_2B_1)]}{B^3 l_1 l_2 l_3 \cos \Delta \sin^2 \Delta} \quad (35)$$

Of course, C^{-1} can be evaluated by using the equations above. However, substituting the algebraic equivalents of the C_{ij} which we have derived into these equations is rather cumbersome. Instead, in machine computation, it is perhaps advisable to substitute numerical values of C_{ij} step by step.

$$\gamma = \frac{B \sin \Delta \begin{pmatrix} B_2 a_{03} - B_3 a_{02} & -(B_1 a_{03} - B_3 a_{01}) & B_1 a_{02} - B_2 a_{01} \\ A_2 a_{03} - A_3 a_{02} & -(A_1 a_{03} - A_3 a_{01}) & A_1 a_{02} - A_2 a_{01} \\ (A_2 B_3 - A_3 B_2) / \tan \Delta & -(A_1 B_3 - A_3 B_1) / \tan \Delta & (A_1 B_2 - A_2 B_1) / \tan \Delta \end{pmatrix}}{a_{01}(A_2 B_3 - A_3 B_2) + a_{02}(A_3 B_1 - A_1 B_3) + a_{03}(A_1 B_2 - A_2 B_1)} \quad (36)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{B \begin{bmatrix} (B_2 a_{03} - B_3 a_{02}) \sin \Delta & -(B_1 a_{03} - B_3 a_{01}) \sin \Delta & (B_1 a_{02} - B_2 a_{01}) \sin \Delta \\ (A_2 a_{03} - A_3 a_{02}) \sin \Delta & -(A_1 a_{03} - A_3 a_{01}) \sin \Delta & (A_1 a_{02} - A_2 a_{01}) \sin \Delta \\ (A_2 B_3 - A_3 B_2) \cos \Delta & -(A_1 B_3 - A_3 B_1) \cos \Delta & (A_1 B_2 - A_2 B_1) \cos \Delta \end{bmatrix}}{a_{01} (A_2 B_3 - A_3 B_2) + a_{02} (A_3 B_1 - A_1 B_3) + a_{03} (A_1 B_2 - A_2 B_1)} \quad (37)$$

Note: The denominator of the equation above is not the determinant of the matrix ($l C$), because factors in the numerator and denominator have cancelled out.

If we let $d = a_{01} (A_2 B_3 - A_3 B_2) + a_{02} (A_3 B_1 - A_1 B_3) + a_{03} (A_1 B_2 - A_2 B_1)$,

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{11} &= B (B_2 a_{03} - B_3 a_{02}) \sin \Delta / d \\ \gamma_{12} &= -B (B_1 a_{03} - B_3 a_{01}) \sin \Delta / d \\ \gamma_{13} &= B (B_1 a_{02} - B_2 a_{01}) \sin \Delta / d \\ \gamma_{21} &= B (A_2 a_{03} - A_3 a_{02}) \sin \Delta / d \\ \gamma_{22} &= -B (A_1 a_{03} - A_3 a_{01}) \sin \Delta / d \\ \gamma_{23} &= B (A_1 a_{02} - A_2 a_{01}) \sin \Delta / d \\ \gamma_{31} &= B (A_2 B_3 - A_3 B_2) \cos \Delta / d \\ \gamma_{32} &= -B (A_1 B_3 - A_3 B_1) \cos \Delta / d \\ \gamma_{33} &= B (A_1 B_2 - A_2 B_1) \cos \Delta / d \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

$$B_{case} = \gamma \Phi \quad \Rightarrow \quad \begin{pmatrix} B_x(\alpha) \\ B_y(\alpha) \\ B_z(\alpha) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma_{11} & \gamma_{12} & \gamma_{13} \\ \gamma_{21} & \gamma_{22} & \gamma_{23} \\ \gamma_{31} & \gamma_{32} & \gamma_{33} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varphi_u(\alpha) \\ \varphi_v(\alpha) \\ \varphi_w(\alpha) \end{pmatrix}$$

that is,

$$\boxed{\begin{aligned} B_x &= \gamma_{11} \varphi_u + \gamma_{12} \varphi_v + \gamma_{13} \varphi_w \\ B_y &= \gamma_{21} \varphi_u + \gamma_{22} \varphi_v + \gamma_{23} \varphi_w \\ B_z &= \gamma_{31} \varphi_u + \gamma_{32} \varphi_v + \gamma_{33} \varphi_w \end{aligned}} \quad (39)$$

This is the set of equations that we had set out to obtain.

1.1.5 Determine the Magnetic Static Sensitivities l_1 , l_2 and l_3 .

Prior to these measurements, the magnetic static sensitivities will most likely have been independently measured by the investigator. However, after conducting these measurements, we are able to compute the best-fit static sensitivities based upon the Fourier analysis of the data. We address this forthwith.

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_u(\alpha) &= l_1 B_u = a_{01} + A_1 \cos \alpha + B_1 \sin \alpha \\ \varphi_v(\alpha) &= l_2 B_v = a_{02} + A_2 \cos \alpha + B_2 \sin \alpha \\ \varphi_w(\alpha) &= l_3 B_w = a_{03} + A_3 \cos \alpha + B_3 \sin \alpha\end{aligned}$$

Since $\Delta = D + 90^\circ$, $\sin \Delta = \cos D$, $\cos \Delta = -\sin D$ and $\tan \Delta = -\cot D$.

In the following derivations we consider how to determine from measurements, what is the orientation of the sensor-axes of a 3 axis flux-gate magnetometer relative to the case or housing in which it is installed. We use an Euler angle rotation matrix $E(\theta, \phi, \psi)$ for this purpose. The Euler angles are used in this paper to indicate the 3 dimensional orientation of the non-orthogonal sensor-axes (u, v, w) of the magnetometer relative to the orthogonal case-axes (x, y, z) of the sensor package.

The constants $a_{01}, a_{02}, a_{03}, A_1, B_1, A_2, B_2, A_3, B_3$ will be evaluated in terms of angles $\theta_1, \phi_1, \psi_1, \theta_2, \phi_2, \psi_2, \theta_3, \phi_3, \psi_3$ instead of simply three angles θ, ϕ, ψ . The phrases "flux detector" and "flux-gate" are used interchangeably. The phrase "Euler rotations" as used in this paper refers to matrix transformations of components of a vector in one orthogonal coordinate system into another via the Euler rotation matrix.

A few definitions:

N, W, V : The orthogonal space-axis coordinates on the surface of the earth. N and W lie in the horizontal plane, and V is the local vertical axis. N is positive towards magnetic north, W is positive toward west, and V is positive vertically upward.

u, v, w : Non-orthogonal sensor-axis coordinates of the magnetometer.

x, y, z : Orthogonal case-axis coordinates of the magnetometer. Ideally, i.e., if there were no orthogonality errors, $x = u, y = v, z = w$.

All angles θ, ϕ, ψ are measured in the standard manner in mathematics, increasing positively in the sense of a right hand screw.

Figure 3: The Euler Angle Rotations.

The orientation of the non-orthogonal sensor coordinate system $S_{sens}(u, v, w)$ relative to the orthogonal case-axes coordinate system $S_{case}(x, y, z)$ is given by *modified* Euler rotations. If the coordinate system $S_{sens}(u, v, w)$ were orthogonal, we would write

$$\begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix} = E(\theta, \phi, \psi) \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} \Rightarrow \begin{pmatrix} B_u \\ B_v \\ B_w \end{pmatrix} \stackrel{\text{(If sensor axes were orthogonal to one-another)}}{=} E(\theta, \phi, \psi) \begin{pmatrix} B_x \\ B_y \\ B_z \end{pmatrix} \quad (40)$$

and the orientation of the orthogonal case-axes coordinate system $S_{case}(x, y, z)$ relative to the orthogonal laboratory coordinate system $S_0(x_0, y_0, z_0)$ would be simply

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{pmatrix} = Z(\alpha) \begin{pmatrix} x_0 \\ y_0 \\ z_0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \alpha & \sin \alpha & 0 \\ -\sin \alpha & \cos \alpha & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x_0 \\ y_0 \\ z_0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (41)$$

$E(\theta, \phi, \psi) = Z(\theta) \cdot X(\phi) \cdot Z(\psi)$ is the Euler angle rotation matrix,

$$\begin{aligned} E(\theta, \phi, \psi) &= \begin{pmatrix} \cos \psi & \sin \psi & 0 \\ -\sin \psi & \cos \psi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \phi & \sin \phi \\ 0 & -\sin \phi & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & \sin \theta & 0 \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta \cos \psi - \sin \theta \cos \phi \sin \psi & \sin \theta \cos \psi + \cos \theta \cos \phi \sin \psi & \sin \phi \sin \psi \\ -\cos \theta \sin \psi - \sin \theta \cos \phi \cos \psi & -\sin \theta \sin \psi + \cos \theta \cos \phi \cos \psi & \sin \phi \cos \psi \\ \sin \theta \sin \phi & -\cos \theta \sin \phi & \cos \phi \end{pmatrix} \quad (42) \end{aligned}$$

and, as we have shown,

$$B_{case} = \begin{pmatrix} B_x \\ B_y \\ B_z \end{pmatrix} = B \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta \cos \alpha \\ -\sin \Delta \sin \alpha \\ \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix} = B \begin{pmatrix} \cos D \cos \alpha \\ -\cos D \sin \alpha \\ -\sin D \end{pmatrix}$$

*Orthogonal
Sensor-Axes
Components
(Actual sensor)*

$$\text{So, } \begin{pmatrix} B_u/B \\ B_v/B \\ B_w/B \end{pmatrix} = E(\theta, \phi, \psi) \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta \cos \alpha \\ -\sin \Delta \sin \alpha \\ \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varphi_u(\alpha)/l_1 B \\ \varphi_v(\alpha)/l_2 B \\ \varphi_w(\alpha)/l_3 B \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} B_u/B \\ B_v/B \\ B_w/B \end{pmatrix} = E(\theta, \phi, \psi) \begin{pmatrix} \sin \Delta \cos \alpha \\ -\sin \Delta \sin \alpha \\ \cos \Delta \end{pmatrix}$$

However, the coordinate system $S_{sens}(u, v, w)$ in general is not orthogonal, so we must modify the Euler rotation matrix somewhat.

The 3 axis magnetometer is installed in this package with the intention of having one sensor-axis directed along each of the case-axes.

Repeating, *ideally*, the sensor-axes u, v, w are the same as the case-axes x, y, z . But ideal situations do not always prevail. A small measure of non-orthogonality between the flux-gate sensor-axes will occur, because of the difficulty in their placement and difficulty in accurately ascertaining the orientation of the magnetic axes relative to the case axes. There will usually be some alignment error, albeit small.

Equations for computing the sensor alignment errors based upon the azimuth table measurements will be presented, using **a modified Euler rotation matrix which we shall designate as U** . In the modified matrix, the Euler angles θ, ϕ, ψ are replaced by angles θ_1, ϕ_1, ψ_1 in the first row of the rotation matrix for sensor-axis u ; they are replaced by θ_2, ϕ_2, ψ_2 in the second row of the rotation matrix for sensor-axis v ; and they are replaced by θ_3, ϕ_3, ψ_3 in the third row of the rotation matrix for sensor-axis w . These modified Euler angle coordinate transformations are required for the purpose of computing the magnetic static sensitivities of the sensors. Thus,

$$U = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta_1 \cos \psi_1 - \sin \theta_1 \cos \phi_1 \sin \psi_1 & \sin \theta_1 \cos \psi_1 + \cos \theta_1 \cos \phi_1 \sin \psi_1 & \sin \phi_1 \sin \psi_1 \\ -\cos \theta_2 \sin \psi_2 - \sin \theta_2 \cos \phi_2 \cos \psi_2 & -\sin \theta_2 \sin \psi_2 + \cos \theta_2 \cos \phi_2 \cos \psi_2 & \sin \phi_2 \cos \psi_2 \\ \sin \theta_3 \sin \phi_3 & -\cos \theta_3 \sin \phi_3 & \cos \phi_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (43)$$

That is,

$$\begin{aligned}
U_{11} &= \cos \theta_1 \cos \psi_1 - \sin \theta_1 \cos \phi_1 \sin \psi_1 \\
U_{12} &= \sin \theta_1 \cos \psi_1 + \cos \theta_1 \cos \phi_1 \sin \psi_1 \\
U_{13} &= \sin \phi_1 \sin \psi_1 \\
U_{21} &= -\cos \theta_2 \sin \psi_2 - \sin \theta_2 \cos \phi_2 \cos \psi_2 \\
U_{22} &= -\sin \theta_2 \sin \psi_2 + \cos \theta_2 \cos \phi_2 \cos \psi_2 \\
U_{23} &= \sin \phi_2 \cos \psi_2 \\
U_{31} &= \sin \theta_3 \sin \phi_3 \\
U_{32} &= -\cos \theta_3 \sin \phi_3 \\
U_{33} &= \cos \phi_3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
u &= U_{11} x + U_{12} y + U_{13} z & B_u &= U_{11} B_x + U_{12} B_y + U_{13} B_z \\
v &= U_{21} x + U_{22} y + U_{23} z & B_v &= U_{21} B_x + U_{22} B_y + U_{23} B_z \\
w &= U_{31} x + U_{32} y + U_{33} z & B_w &= U_{31} B_x + U_{32} B_y + U_{33} B_z
\end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
B_u &= (\cos \theta_1 \cos \psi_1 - \sin \theta_1 \cos \phi_1 \sin \psi_1) B_x \\
&\quad + (\sin \theta_1 \cos \psi_1 + \cos \theta_1 \cos \phi_1 \sin \psi_1) B_y + (\sin \phi_1 \sin \psi_1) B_z \\
B_v &= (-\cos \theta_2 \sin \psi_2 - \sin \theta_2 \cos \phi_2 \cos \psi_2) B_x \\
&\quad + (-\sin \theta_2 \sin \psi_2 + \cos \theta_2 \cos \phi_2 \cos \psi_2) B_y + (\sin \phi_2 \cos \psi_2) B_z \\
B_w &= (\sin \theta_3 \sin \phi_3) B_x + (-\cos \theta_3 \sin \phi_3) B_y + (\cos \phi_3) B_z
\end{aligned}$$

$$B_u = U_{11} (B \sin \Delta \cos \alpha) + U_{12} (-B \sin \Delta \sin \alpha) + U_{13} (B \cos \Delta) \quad (44)$$

$$= \frac{\varphi_u}{l_1} = \frac{A_1}{l_1} \cos \alpha + \frac{B_1}{l_1} \sin \alpha + \frac{a_{01}}{l_1} \Rightarrow \quad (45)$$

$$A_1 = l_1 B U_{11} \sin \Delta = l_1 B (\cos \theta_1 \cos \psi_1 - \cos \phi_1 \sin \theta_1 \sin \psi_1) \sin \Delta$$

$$B_1 = l_1 B U_{12} \sin \Delta = -l_1 B (\sin \theta_1 \cos \psi_1 + \cos \phi_1 \cos \theta_1 \sin \psi_1) \sin \Delta$$

$$a_{01} = l_1 B U_{13} \cos \Delta = l_1 B \sin \phi_1 \sin \psi_1 \cos \Delta \quad (46)$$

$$H_1^2 = A_1^2 + B_1^2 \Rightarrow H_1 = l_1 B \sin \Delta \sqrt{\cos^2 \phi_1 \sin^2 \psi_1 + \cos^2 \psi_1}$$

Similarly for B_v ,

$$B_v = U_{21} (B \sin \Delta \cos \alpha) + U_{22} (-B \sin \Delta \sin \alpha) + U_{23} (B \cos \Delta) \quad (47)$$

$$= \frac{\varphi_v}{l_2} = \frac{A_2}{l_2} \cos \alpha + \frac{B_2}{l_2} \sin \alpha + \frac{a_{02}}{l_2} \Rightarrow \quad (48)$$

$$A_2 = l_2 B U_{21} \sin \Delta = -l_2 B (\cos \theta_2 \sin \psi_2 + \sin \theta_2 \cos \phi_2 \cos \psi_2) \sin \Delta$$

$$B_2 = l_2 B U_{22} \sin \Delta = l_2 B (\sin \theta_2 \sin \psi_2 - \cos \theta_2 \cos \phi_2 \cos \psi_2) \sin \Delta$$

$$a_{02} = l_2 B U_{23} \cos \Delta = l_2 B \sin \phi_2 \cos \psi_2 \cos \Delta \quad (49)$$

$$H_2^2 = A_2^2 + B_2^2 \Rightarrow H_2 = l_2 B \sin \Delta \sqrt{\cos^2 \phi_2 \cos^2 \psi_2 + \sin^2 \psi_2}$$

and

$$B_w = U_{31} (B \sin \Delta \cos \alpha) + U_{32} (-B \sin \Delta \sin \alpha) + U_{33} (B \cos \Delta) \quad (50)$$

$$= \frac{\varphi_w}{l_3} = \frac{A_3}{l_3} \cos \alpha + \frac{B_3}{l_3} \sin \alpha + \frac{a_{03}}{l_3} \Rightarrow \quad (51)$$

$$A_3 = l_3 B U_{31} \sin \Delta = l_3 B \sin \theta_3 \sin \phi_3 \sin \Delta$$

$$B_3 = l_3 B U_{32} \sin \Delta = l_3 B \cos \theta_3 \sin \phi_3 \sin \Delta$$

$$a_{03} = l_3 B U_{33} = l_3 B \cos \phi_3 \cos \Delta \quad (52)$$

$$H_3^2 = A_3^2 + B_3^2 \Rightarrow H_3 = l_3 B \sin \phi_3 \sin \Delta$$

Continuing with this line of thought,

$$H_1 = l_1 B \sin \Delta \sqrt{\cos^2 \phi_1 \sin^2 \psi_1 + \cos^2 \psi_1}, \quad a_{01} = l_1 B \cos \Delta \sin \phi_1 \sin \psi_1$$

$$\text{Then } H_1^2 + a_{01}^2 \tan^2 \Delta$$

$$= (l_1 B \sin \Delta)^2 (\cos^2 \phi_1 \sin^2 \psi_1 + \cos^2 \psi_1) + (l_1 B \cos \Delta)^2 \tan^2 \Delta \sin^2 \phi_1 \sin^2 \psi_1 \Rightarrow$$

$$H_1^2 + a_{01}^2 \tan^2 \Delta = (l_1 B \sin \Delta)^2 \Rightarrow \boxed{l_1 = \frac{\sqrt{H_1^2 + a_{01}^2 \tan^2 \Delta}}{B \sin \Delta} = \frac{\sqrt{H_1^2 + a_{01}^2 \cot^2 D}}{B \cos D}} \quad (53)$$

Likewise,

$$H_2 = l_2 B \sin \Delta \sqrt{\cos^2 \phi_2 \cos^2 \psi_2 + \sin^2 \psi_2}, \quad a_{02} = l_2 B \sin \phi_2 \cos \psi_2 \cos \Delta$$

$$\text{Then } H_2^2 + a_{02}^2 \tan^2 \Delta$$

$$= (l_2 B \sin \Delta)^2 (\cos^2 \phi_2 \cos^2 \psi_2 + \sin^2 \psi_2) + (l_2 B)^2 \sin^2 \phi_2 \cos^2 \psi_2 \cos^2 \Delta \frac{\sin^2 \Delta}{\cos^2 \Delta} \Rightarrow$$

$$H_2^2 + a_{02}^2 \tan^2 \Delta = (l_2 B \sin \Delta)^2 \Rightarrow \boxed{l_2 = \frac{\sqrt{H_2^2 + a_{02}^2 \tan^2 \Delta}}{B \sin \Delta} = \frac{\sqrt{H_2^2 + a_{02}^2 \cot^2 D}}{B \cos D}} \quad (54)$$

and

$$H_3 = l_3 B \sin \phi_3 \sin \Delta, \quad a_{03} = l_3 B \cos \phi_3 \cos \Delta$$

$$\text{Then } H_3^2 + a_{03}^2 \tan^2 \Delta$$

$$= (l_3 B \sin \phi_3 \sin \Delta)^2 + (l_3 B \cos \phi_3 \cos \Delta)^2 \frac{\sin^2 \Delta}{\cos^2 \Delta} = (l_3 B \sin \Delta)^2$$

$$H_3^2 + a_{03}^2 \tan^2 \Delta = (l_3 B \sin \Delta)^2 \Rightarrow \boxed{l_3 = \frac{\sqrt{H_3^2 + a_{03}^2 \tan^2 \Delta}}{B \sin \Delta} = \frac{\sqrt{H_3^2 + a_{03}^2 \cot^2 D}}{B \cos D}} \quad (55)$$

Although these are not needed for further computation, for completeness of this discussion we shall express the various c_{ij} in terms of the angles $\theta_1, \phi_1, \psi_1, \theta_2, \phi_2, \psi_2, \theta_3, \phi_3, \psi_3$.

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{11} &= \frac{A_1}{l_1 B \sin \Delta} = \frac{A_1}{l_1 B \cos D} = \frac{l_1 B (\cos \theta_1 \cos \psi_1 - \cos \phi_1 \sin \theta_1 \sin \psi_1) \sin \Delta}{l_1 B \sin \Delta} \\
&= \cos \theta_1 \cos \psi_1 - \cos \phi_1 \sin \theta_1 \sin \psi_1 = U_{11} \\
C_{12} &= -\frac{B_1}{l_1 B \sin \Delta} = -\frac{B_1}{l_1 B \cos D} = -\frac{-l_1 B (\sin \theta_1 \cos \psi_1 + \cos \phi_1 \cos \theta_1 \sin \psi_1) \sin \Delta}{l_1 B \sin \Delta} \\
&= \sin \theta_1 \cos \psi_1 + \cos \phi_1 \cos \theta_1 \sin \psi_1 = U_{12} \\
C_{13} &= \frac{a_{01}}{l_1 B \cos \Delta} = -\frac{a_{01}}{l_1 B \sin D} = \frac{l_1 B \sin \phi_1 \sin \psi_1 \cos \Delta}{l_1 B \cos \Delta} = \sin \phi_1 \sin \psi_1 = U_{13} \\
C_{21} &= \frac{A_2}{l_2 B \sin \Delta} = \frac{A_2}{l_2 B \cos D} = \frac{-l_2 B (\cos \theta_2 \sin \psi_2 + \sin \theta_2 \cos \phi_2 \cos \psi_2) \sin \Delta}{l_2 B \sin \Delta} \\
&= -(\cos \theta_2 \sin \psi_2 + \sin \theta_2 \cos \phi_2 \cos \psi_2) = U_{21} \\
C_{22} &= -\frac{B_2}{l_2 B \sin \Delta} = -\frac{B_2}{l_2 B \cos D} = -\frac{l_2 B (\sin \theta_2 \sin \psi_2 - \cos \theta_2 \cos \phi_2 \cos \psi_2) \sin \Delta}{l_2 B \sin \Delta} \\
&= -(\sin \theta_2 \sin \psi_2 - \cos \theta_2 \cos \phi_2 \cos \psi_2) = U_{22} \\
C_{23} &= \frac{a_{02}}{l_2 B \cos \Delta} = -\frac{a_{02}}{l_2 B \sin D} = \frac{l_2 B \sin \phi_2 \cos \psi_2 \cos \Delta}{l_2 B \cos \Delta} = \sin \phi_2 \cos \psi_2 = U_{23} \\
C_{31} &= \frac{A_3}{l_3 B \sin \Delta} = \frac{A_3}{l_3 B \cos D} = \frac{l_3 B \sin \theta_3 \sin \phi_3 \sin \Delta}{l_3 B \sin \Delta} = \sin \theta_3 \sin \phi_3 = U_{31} \\
C_{32} &= -\frac{B_3}{l_3 B \sin \Delta} = -\frac{B_3}{l_3 B \cos D} = -\frac{l_3 B \cos \theta_3 \sin \phi_3 \sin \Delta}{l_3 B \sin \Delta} = -\cos \theta_3 \sin \phi_3 = U_{32} \\
C_{33} &= \frac{a_{03}}{l_3 B \cos \Delta} = -\frac{a_{03}}{l_3 B \sin D} = \frac{l_3 B \cos \phi_3 \cos \Delta}{l_3 B \cos \Delta} = \cos \phi_3 = U_{33}
\end{aligned} \tag{56}$$

2 Appendix

2.1 An Algorithm For Integrating the Computing Tasks

Procedure For Determining Direction Cosines, Direction Cosine Angles, and Correction Matrix For a Non-Orthogonal Three-Axis Magnetometer:

Begin procedure.

- Mount the 3-axis magnetometer on a rotary test fixture (an azimuth table) with the z case-axis vertical and pointing up, the x case-axis in the horizontal

plane and pointing to magnetic north and the y case-axis in the horizontal plane pointing west and in the horizontal plane. Run a computer program to record and process data.

- Reply to queries in the program: For example, date of test, magnitude of total local geomagnetic field intensity B in gauss (x.xxx), the local magnetic dip angle D in degrees (xx.x).
- Rotate the probe in azimuth, Z . Select an even number N of equally spaced azimuth angles (angles in navigational format), and measure and record the DC output voltages from each of the strap-down magnetic sensors at these angles. These voltages are designated as $\varphi_u(Z)$, $\varphi_v(Z)$, $\varphi_w(Z)$, where Z is azimuth. The computer program should record the equivalent data in standard mathematical format; that is, record $\varphi_u(\alpha)$, $\varphi_v(\alpha)$, $\varphi_w(\alpha)$, where $\alpha = 360^\circ - Z$ is co-azimuth (standard mathematical angle format). In computer programs, since most computer programming environments do not use Greek letters, we may use the following symbol replacements: $\varphi_u \leftarrow mu$, $\varphi_v \leftarrow mv$, $\varphi_w \leftarrow mw$, $\varphi_x \leftarrow mx$, $\varphi_y \leftarrow my$, $\varphi_z \leftarrow mz$.
- Use Simpson's rule of numerical integration to Fourier analyze this voltage data and determine the parameters a_{01} , A_1 , B_1 , a_{02} , A_2 , B_2 , a_{03} , A_3 , B_3 of the three equations

$$\begin{aligned}\varphi_u(\alpha) &= a_{01} + A_1 \cos \alpha + B_1 \sin \alpha \\ \varphi_v(\alpha) &= a_{02} + A_2 \cos \alpha + B_2 \sin \alpha \\ \varphi_w(\alpha) &= a_{03} + A_3 \cos \alpha + B_3 \sin \alpha\end{aligned}$$

- Compute the amplitudes $H_1 = \sqrt{A_1^2 + B_1^2}$, $H_2 = \sqrt{A_2^2 + B_2^2}$, $H_3 = \sqrt{A_3^2 + B_3^2}$ and the magnetometer best-fit static sensitivities l_1, l_2, l_3 in volts/gauss, using $l_1 = \frac{\sqrt{H_1^2 + a_1^2 \cot^2 D}}{B \cos D}$, $l_2 = \frac{\sqrt{H_2^2 + a_2^2 \cot^2 D}}{B \cos D}$, $l_3 = \frac{\sqrt{H_3^2 + a_3^2 \cot^2 D}}{B \cos D}$.
- Compute $\mathbf{B}(\alpha)_{sensor}$ components, that is, $B_u(\alpha) = \frac{\varphi_u(\alpha)}{l_1}$, $B_v(\alpha) = \frac{\varphi_v(\alpha)}{l_2}$, $B_w(\alpha) = \frac{\varphi_w(\alpha)}{l_3}$.
- Noting that $\alpha = 360^\circ - Z$, perform this replacement and obtain $\mathbf{B}_{sens}(Z)$ components, that is, $B_u(Z) = \frac{\varphi_u(Z)}{l_1}$, $B_v(Z) = \frac{\varphi_v(Z)}{l_2}$, $B_w(Z) = \frac{\varphi_w(Z)}{l_3}$.
- Compute the nine direction cosines C_{ij} .
- Compute the nine direction cosine angles, $\alpha_{ij} = \arcsin C_{ij}$.

- Compute the inverse of the modified direction cosine matrix $\gamma = (l C)^{-1}$.
- Compute $B(\alpha)_{case}$ (or $B(Z)_{case}$) $= \gamma \Phi$, that is

$$\begin{aligned} B_x &= \gamma_{11} \varphi_u + \gamma_{12} \varphi_v + \gamma_{13} \varphi_w \\ B_y &= \gamma_{21} \varphi_u + \gamma_{22} \varphi_v + \gamma_{23} \varphi_w \\ B_z &= \gamma_{31} \varphi_u + \gamma_{32} \varphi_v + \gamma_{33} \varphi_w \end{aligned}$$

■ END.